

Research

A relative study of clustering data mining in the education sector of Bangladesh

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Abstract: Clustering Data mining is extracting knowledge from data using data analysis tools to conduct pattern recognition and predictive modeling tasks. It is a common technique for statistical data, machine learning, and computer-science analysis. Clustering is a kind of unsupervised data mining technique that describes general working behavior and pattern extraction and extracts valuable information from electricity price time series. This article explains data mining technology to analyze educational data from Bangladesh universities' using various types of clustering data mining techniques- Partitioning Clustering, Hierarchical Clustering, Grid-based clustering, Model-based clustering, and Density-based clustering. The event logs acquired from the natural e-course e-learning environment were used for the analysis. This investigation used cluster analysis and decision trees as data mining approaches. Cluster analysis divided the students into groups based on their behavior when using the material. It was a method that I was interested in generating a decision expression that could define a class of objects for a detailed analysis of how the decision tree students learned.

Keywords: Data mining, cluster, bioprocess, pattern, Process Mining, Process Analysis

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Introduction

Data mining is a popular method of examining big data sets to extract valuable or necessary information. Data mining applications uncover hidden data patterns and find correlations between parameters in large volumes of data. Educational data mining is analyzing educational data using data mining techniques. 1. A huge database holds a variety of training data. This is particularly true if you can capture and save online programs, curriculum support, and student learning behavior. A learning management system is the most prevalent type of information system. 2. Many schools evaluate student performance based on final grades, but to accomplish an effective and consistent learning process, they rely on course structure assessments and learning goals.

This article examines students' behavior in a real e-course for a semester using cluster analysis and decision tree approaches. The data utilized in the analysis is an event log for the 2017/2018 student generation retrieved from the e-

learning system of an e-course at a higher education institution in Bangladesh. The log file is where the information system records are saved, and the data is known as the event log.

Cluster analysis is a method for categorizing a set of ordered patterns based on a shared trait or behavior. A five-cluster analysis is one of the most intriguing areas of application, as it is employed in education and data mining for various objectives. Students are grouped to uncover common behavioral patterns.

A decision tree's purpose is to identify a particular object's class. It uses the properties of other things in the decision tree to classify a subset of different objects. It does not use a single attribute or a fixed set of characteristics. The appeal of the seven decision trees is that they are easy to understand and interpret.

This study aims to see if student behavioral elements captured in the e-learning system can help students pass the exam in the e-course under investigation. The following are the research questions that this article aims to answer:

1. Is it possible to extract student information from the event log of the e-learning system?
2. What are the values of factors in the e-learning system that significantly impact categorizing pupils according to student behavior?

The inspiration for producing this essay stems from the fact that there are many fascinating processes to examine for the actions of many students who can use advanced data mining techniques to improve the content management of that process. The quality of e-course implementation in Bangladesh higher education institutions indicates the quality of education based on the institution's ranking.

A literature review is a study of previously published material. This chapter teaches you about education, data mining, log application, cluster analysis, and decision tree approaches. The research methodology given in Naagai's book aims to introduce research data and research procedures. Following is a post-methodological explanation of the cluster analysis and decision tree results. A concluding discussion statement for acknowledged knowledge and future work concludes the paper.

Literature review

The log could contain a wide range of data related to the process's activity. Data mining shares some characteristics with automated process search technologies. Data mining includes these automated process search technologies in the academic subject of process mining because they "extract meaningful information from fragmented data."

Data mining is extracting useful information and knowledge from a large data warehouse. This includes applying data analysis tools to detect relationships with unknown patterns in large datasets. "Data mining, decision tree setting, rule judo, artificial neural network, instance-based learning, Bayesian learning, logical programming, statistical algorithms, etc." Also, the most helpful data mining operations and Methods are statistics, visualization, clustering, classification, and related rule mining. These methods represent new, exciting, and valuable knowledge based on available information.

Applying data mining technology for educational data is called educational data mining. In education, the primary purpose of using data mining technology is to develop models that can predict the overall performance of students in selected courses.

To improve your education level:

- Create a data source for predictors.
- Identification of various characteristics or factors that affect students' learning outcomes in school.
- Build predictive models using classification data mining techniques based on predictive variables.
- Validation of models developed based on the achievements of students learning.

Many databases contain student information, so you can work with large data stores that reflect student learning practices. Folino et al. investigated using a decision tree guidance approach in external memory to handle large logs efficiently. Data mining technology provides economically adjustable education, effectively improving systems and reducing the cost of the education process. Higher education institutions enhance the quality of teaching and use various methods to analyze and develop their understanding of student achievement. Student data can be used in education and learning to create and configure predictive models to identify student outcomes. "By extracting, we can get information from the data and create process models that show scenarios for the various education processes." Asif et al. The purpose of prediction in educational data mining is to predict the outcome of a student's education. An example of using data mining techniques in an e-learning process is to evaluate student learning outcomes, ensure course coordination, and generate learning recommendations based on student behavior. Learning, teaching materials, and curriculum assessments provide feedback to teachers and students and discover unusual student behavior during education.

Several methods have been developed to solve the classification problem. Of all these methods, it is considered appropriate as it is regarded as one of the most commonly used methods for learning decision tree maps.

Decision Tree A classification algorithm that displays both types of nodes in a branched tree format. The decision tree is guided through the map knowledge discovery process using pre-class knowledge. Channel new knowledge. Tree Logical Attribute, A decision tree instance consists of internal nodes that match the test, and a connection branch that shows the test results is placed under the tree from the root to the leaf node to classify the instances. The decision tree decides whether to approve or reject a particular value. Using IF-THEN rules, the current state is mapped to a future state and considered a procedure for making other decisions. IF-THEN rule is one. It is the most popular form of knowledge representation because it is easy for non-professionals to understand, interpret, and apply directly to decision-making. It uses a decision tree to reach its leaves, forms a continuous path, and shows a particular display. Every node in the tree corresponds to a subset of the data. Ideally, the leaf is beautiful. All leaf elements have the same probability of being the target variable or class. In learning using a decision tree, target variables refer to attributes. Each attribute node divides the set of instances into multiple subsets. The root of the tree corresponds to all cases.

The decision tree is easy to understand and often applies to classification issues. It is a natural model with few regressions, plagued by the sensitivity of the data used in its construction. The advantage of decision trees is that many efficient algorithms can roughly find the optimal tree architecture. You can also subdivide complex decision-making problems in the decision tree into several simple issues.

To build a decision tree:

1. Suppose C is a set of objects to classify starting from the current node. If all members in set C are of the same class or C is empty, make sure the current node is a leaf node, label it according to its course, and complete the procedure. Otherwise, go to step 2.
2. Suppose A_i is the selected attribute of the current node. The characteristics of A_i have possible values with $V_i = \{A_{i1}, A_{i2}, \dots, A_{iv}\}$.
3. Use the property's value to split the set of objects C into mutually exclusive and complete subsets $\{C_{i1}, C_{i2}, \dots, C_{iv}\}$ Each subset of C_{ij} contains objects in C whose attribute A_i has a value of A_{ij} .
4. Create child nodes in the tree for each attribute of the A_{ij} value and its subset of C_{ij} . Then use the following property value A_{ij} to label the issues from the current node to the child nodes.
5. Recursively call the subset C_{ij} steps using the set of available attributes $\{A - A_i\}$.for each child node.

Child nodes are drawn to the parent's right and can be used to forecast and identify future pupils based on the actions and decisions of the decision tree. Decision nodes are commonly presented as rectangles. Tree format is sometimes used to convey classifications. The purpose is to create a decision tree model that will be used to forecast cluster membership for future enactment based on knowledge of the data associated with executing several traces. The decision tree is easier to understand than other database systems, and the application does not require advanced computer skills.

Methodology

The research approach utilized to conduct the analysis is presented in this paragraph. First, we provide a cluster analysis and decision-making tree method-based education and data mining model. The data source and data type are then explained.

The educational data mining model

The actions depicted in Figure 1 are partially acknowledged as essential activities in educational data mining utilizing cluster analysis and decision tree techniques, according to the literature reviewed in the previous phase.

Figure 1. Educational data mining process using cluster analysis and decision tree technique.

To begin, choose the dataset you wish to study, which is the target e-course. After selecting the e-course in the e-learning environment, you must download the log file. We can supply the following education and data mining stage based on the downloaded event log. After downloading and saving the data, you may begin the data cleaning process. This process includes data analyst analysis, data cleansing, and data separation of redundant and irrelevant data. Data partitioning occurs after the data cleansing procedure. This means that relevant data will be extracted and merged for future research.

This exercise is based on data mining techniques and the analysis findings. Cluster analysis can establish similar groupings within a group and sets of other students if your data is manageable. According to these groups, different data mining techniques (e.g., decision tree approaches) can be used for the collected data. Once you get the data from the cluster analysis, you may prepare it for the export decision tree technology. You can validate your model if you have one from previous activity. The analyst's results tell you how to control your model's accuracy. The resulting model can be understood depending on the results after examining the model's validation.

Data description

The data utilized in the analysis is an event log for the 2017/2018 student generation from a Croatian higher education institution's e-course e-learning system. The data was collected between February and June of this year. Initially, there were 62,985 records; after arranging the data and removing roughly 3000 entries for process management and teaching, 59,605 documents remained for analysis. Access date and time, student name, context (e.g., lecture material), components (e.g., "record"), activity description, source (e.g., "Web"), and student IP address are all included in these records. The raw data is displayed—the individual who accessed the online course. Data cleansing entails deleting information regarding system administrators' and teachers' activities. It was fascinating to focus solely on student behavior in the e-learning system. In addition, due to data confidentiality and the protection of personal information, only a portion of the anonymized data was retrieved for further research. One hundred eighty-five students enrolled in the e-course during one semester. We paid for two interim examinations in April and June of the same year. Each mid-term exam was given a maximum of 40 points and did not have a minimum scoring requirement. In the e-learning system, the interim assessment results are awarded to each student individually.

As mentioned in previous studies, we have recognized that fewer variables are essential for congestion formation.

1. The "context" of the event log provides e-content type information.
2. A description of the activity related to the activity with its student identification label.

Previous research tried identifying pupils from different generations based on their online activities. Examine the use of context variables by applying them to other datasets (in this case, the 2017/2018 generation). This study takes a more in-depth look at the data and adds additional decision tree approaches to evaluate and understand student behavior.

Access to lecture materials, access to auditory materials, access to laboratory data, and access to forums were the values of the variable "context." The theme tune for the lecture was sent to students who were processed weekly as part of the lecture materials. Students could download the e-learning system's teaching materials before and after the lesson. Students might download and print materials to assist them in staying up with the lectures before Hearing Practice (AE). Each resource took an average of 5 clicks to download. Laboratory practice (LE) was carried out in a laboratory class at a higher education institution, and students were expected to solve issues independently. In the course, students were required to download e-learning materials and click around five times. The forum comprised a discussion forum

where students could ask questions regarding the e-course and engage with one another, as well as a news forum with e-course-related items and teacher consultations where students could have direct conversations with the teacher.

Following the data cleansing, a pivot table was constructed with information about each student's access frequency based on the recorded identification labels. The frequency with which e-content is accessed shows its popularity, and "popularity" can be assessed by the number of e-content requests received throughout the semester. 21 How frequently e-content is accessed, what type of e-content students perceive concerning passing the e-course test, and whether connection frequency impacts the exam's ultimate result. You can do so. 11; as a result, the pivot table includes student-identifying data. Data from students' lectures, AEs, LEs, and forums are accessed via numbers and number frequency format labels. The following data mining technology cluster analysis and decision tree were performed using this table and the RapidMiner22 program. According to the literature, these data mining approaches use a more direct system, such as calculating the percentage of well-classified data. In contrast, statistical techniques typically provide accuracy for given data. The model was chosen because it is utilized as a sex quality standard.

Furthermore, data mining techniques operate with massive amounts of data, whereas statistics struggle with vast, multidimensional databases. The k-means applied algorithm, the number of groups (proven to be the most significant value with promising results), grouping variable is student ID, and Was the method of choice for cluster analysis. The Z-transform was used for normalization, the grouping measurement type was numeric, and the number of measurements chosen was Euclidean distance. Finally, lectures, AE, LE, and the frequency of access to forum contents were selected as influential criteria for grouping. The following are the tool settings for using the decision tree technique: The student rating achieved in two mid-term tests, with a total of 80 points in both mid-term tests, is the target variable for forecasting results. The variable that provides the most information gain is the student score. In addition, the Z-transform was chosen for normalizing, and the decision tree was constructed using least squares. The maximum depth of the bird is 10, and the minimum leaf size is 2, which is the minimal size for division. The number of pre-arranged options was four, and the number of pre-arranged alternatives was three. All decision trees created as a consequence of this study have applied these settings.

The discrepancies are in the minimum gain magnitude:

- Decision tree with cluster number 0: 0.105.
- For a decision tree with cluster number 1: 0.081.
- For a decision tree with cluster number 2: 0.08.

These values were selected for best results quarter and result acceptability for analysis based on previously obtained clustering models.

Results

This study's educational data mining analysis depicts a group of students based on their behavior in an e-learning system and a decision tree based on one model developed by cluster analysis and previous cluster analysis. It was released in three different models. The results of the grouping analysis and decision tree are described in the following section. We also display a box plot of student scores from the mid-term examination to demonstrate the model's validity based on student success—interpretation of the grouping results.

The goal of grouping students was to locate groupings of students within the group that were similar to each other and other groups. The e-learning system's student behavior determines the degree of similarity during the semester. Behavioral intent is a crucial predictor of student conduct and varies depending on the desired action, controls, and normative views.

There are three types of higher education institutes:

- Group 0 contained 84 students.
- Group 1 contained 82 students.
- Group 2 contained 19 students.

Figure 2 depicts a group of students as a tree, whereas Figure 3 depicts a plot depicting the movement of the variable "context" values along a range of medians.

Figure 2. Groups of students.

Figure 3. Movements of the groups according to "Context."

Figure 2 depicts a student group in the shape of a tree. Central Ticket Office Students in Group 0 have the least access to e-Course content, according to Table 1. This category displays activities such as LE and lecture material downloads (weekly). Students in Group 1 have intermediate access to electronic resources. They mostly used things from LE and lectures. Forums are the least used data set in this collection. Group 2 comprises 19 students who regularly access AE, course, and LE materials. Figure 3 is a graph depicting the group's movement based on the value range and center value of the variable "Context." According to these statistics, students in Group 0 have the least access to e-Course content, while students in Group 2 have the most frequent access to e-learning system features.

Table 1. Centroid table.

The value of the variable "Context"	Group 0	Group 1	Group 2
Lectures materials	-0.723	0.385	1.536
Auditory exercises	-0.675	0.223	2.020
Laboratory exercises	-0.784	0.451	1.522
Forums	-0.440	0.115	1.449

Interpretation of the results obtained by the decision tree technique

Following a cluster analysis that divided students into three groups and produced one model, three decision trees based on the groups were built. Each decision tree model represents a group of students' behavior. Figure 4 depicts the conduct of students in group 0 and the decision tree. In contrast, Figure 5 shows the behavior of students in group 1, and Figure 6 illustrates the behavior of students in group 2 and the decision tree. This symbol represents a tree. The student's mid-term exam score represents the highest level of information acquisition. The node represents the e-content courses or the value of the variable "Context," and the support value represents the frequency with which the e-content is accessed.

Figure 4. From the cluster analysis, a decision tree for group 0 was created.

Figure 5. Decision tree for group 1 from the cluster analysis.

Figure 6. Decision tree for group 2 from the cluster analysis.

In a grouping approach, Figure 4 depicts the decision tree model for group 0. Only a few students in this paradigm had the most access to lecture materials. Therefore they had the least access to other electronic stuff. Many of the students in this cohort only had access to lecture materials on a limited basis. Most of the forums were accessed by students who had attended the lecture materials. Access to discussions regularly does not imply access to other forms of electronic

content. Access to forums is limited, as is access to AE resources. Access to AE materials was limited, consequently limiting access to LE materials. Students who scored higher on the test accessed classroom materials and LE data more frequently.

A group 1 decision tree based on cluster analysis is shown in Figure 5. Students use the forum more frequently the more they use the course materials. The lecture materials were limited, and the mid-term exam outcomes were poor. Many students in this cohort used AE course materials and data to complete their assignments. Students in the test group with the best test results appear to understand the relevance of having access to lecture, AE, and LE material combinations. The more you use the AE lecture materials and materials, the better your chances of passing the mid-term exam will be. Group 1 differed from Group 0 in that it consisted of students with intermediate access to all e-content.

Finally, in Figure 6, the final decision tree model depicts the conduct of students in Group 2. This group consisted of 19 students with the most access to minor e-learning system content. Infrequent access to AE and LE resources, as shown in Figure 6, resulted in a low mid-term exam score. Access to LE and AE resources on a more regular basis, more frequent searches of course materials, and higher mid-term exam results. Many students in this category used a combination of all three variables to get excellent marks on the midterm exam.

Because students cannot take courses without a solid theoretical foundation, this analysis must concentrate on the quality of theory-centric materials from the teacher's perspective. There is, as indicated.

Analysis of students' achievement through mid-term exams

The e-course had two mid-term exams that students were able to pass. Up to 40 points were awarded for each mid-term exam. There are two sorts of questions on the interim exam: theory-based (mostly course contents) and task-based (mainly AE and LE materials). The second interim test has been completed. Figure 7 depicts the combined score of the two tests for all e-course students. The Cluster 0 Silver article defines the cluster analysis results in Figure 2 for students in Group 0. The cluster analysis in Figure 2 shows that Cluster 1 contains the students' test results in Group 1. Finally, the cluster 2 cluster analysis displays the points earned by students in group 2. Cluster 0 includes student points that can be described as the least exciting behavior for ongoing materials download, as illustrated in Figure 7. E-learning is a method that allows you to learn from the comfort of your own home. In addition, the pupils in this category obtained the lowest test score. Cluster 1 has various scores for students who have intermediate access to e-learning materials. Some pupils received low grades (less than 10 out of 80), while others received excellent degrees (e.g., 70 or higher). The scores of students with the most access to e-learning materials are found in Cluster 2. This is the highest point in the e-course on the entire planet. The content-related behavioral variables that produce the difference in the scores attained by the students are found in accessing the lecture material, according to the generated group data and the most accessed content for these groups. Students exposed to the lecture materials performed higher on the interim examination.

Figure 7. The points earned by students in midterm exams by the categories to which they belong.

Conclusion

We looked at the domains of education and data mining in this post. With the introduction of big data kept in databases, including records of student behavior in higher education e-course students, this topic has exploded in prominence in recent years. Because of the competition among higher education institutions and the information that students bring to the job market after graduation, academic program quality is exceptionally crucial. Because educational data mining is a subset of data mining, the study in this paper used cluster analysis and decision-making tree techniques. To confirm the author's earlier work, a cluster analysis was performed on a group of students based on their frequency of access to e-content. The decision tree method was applied to the grouping results for a deeper examination of student behavior during education and learning. Course teachers pick information that deserves extra attention based on knowledge gathered through educational data mining to underline the importance of the e-course while students prepare for the exam. You can utilize a better stimulus strategy to persuade people to use that content. In the following study, we'll collect data from other generations and do comparable analyses on other processes in equivalent process settings to see if there are any differences in student behavior and course management between ages. You can concentrate.

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